

Thermal Management Strategies for Low and High Voltage Retrofit LED Lamp Drivers

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Abstract— Several thermal management strategies for LED drivers designed for high lumen retrofit LED lamps are studied by simulation and experimentation means. Depending on the driver output, two scenarios are analyzed: Low Voltage-High Current (18V-620mA) and High Voltage-Low Current (110V-85mA). Experiments (infrared thermography and thermocouples) and multiscale simulation approaches are used to assist both the lamp and driver board thermal design, as well as the driver proper integration in the lighting system. As a result, a heatsink based on an Aluminum hollow cylinder with polymer axial fins is designed and evaluated. The heatsink assessment is carried out with an LED board, in which the LED junction temperature is modeled and extracted by monitoring the LED board backside temperature. Additional experimentation to better integrate the driver is performed aiming at reducing the contact thermal resistance between the driver and the heatsink and improving the heat removal in the driver housing by including a material with a high thermal conductivity (i.e., dry silica sand or magnesium oxide powder). The proposed solution reduces the LED junction temperature up to 18% with respect to a reference lamp, whereas both drivers depict working temperatures around or below 125°C, when an ambient working temperature of 90°C is considered.

Index Terms— Retrofit LED lamp, LED lamp driver, thermal management, infrared thermography, thermocouples.

I. INTRODUCTION

SOLID-STATE Lighting (SSL) starts to be omnipresent in our daily life with notable benefits in comparison to its other competitors, i.e., incandescent, discharge and

fluorescent technologies. SSL offers a more sustainable, effective, and radically efficient residential and commercial lighting with a higher color rendering and impact on energy saving. [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6] Moreover, the use of hazardous and rare metals, traditionally present in Compact Fluorescent Lamps (CFL), are being minimized in LED manufacturing process. [7, 8] In spite of such gains, SSL systems still generate a significant amount of heat, as they convert 20%-40% of the used energy into visible light. [4, 5] Such efficiency is not only limited by the LEDs efficacy, but also to the power dissipation inherent to the driving electronics and light conversion elements of any SSL system. [9] Thus, appropriate heat removal techniques are mandatory to prevent SSL systems from working at temperatures that can eventually compromise their performance, reliability or lifetime [9, 10]. For instance, thermal effects are the responsible for not only their light output reduction or color shift degradation [9], but also the electrolytic capacitors aging in drivers [5, 11] or the solder joint cracking in LED boards [12]. For this reason, one of the main challenges and innovations in SSL is channeled towards its thermal design and assessment approaches to minimize the operation temperature of the LEDs and the driver components [19, 23, 24, 10]. Typically, they have been only devoted to LED thermal optimization by numerical methods [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18], not considering the other lamp parts. However, several works have recently started to claim a design approach at system level taking into account further targets [19, 20, 21, 22]. Such thermal management aspects consider not only the strategies adopted for heat extraction from the LEDs, but also the light conversion elements and the driving electronics to the ambient [19], its thermal simulation and validation [23], and its thermal resistance characterization [24]. Unfortunately, this is not deeply deployed in the current SSL scenario, especially for lifetime and reliability studies [20, 21]. In this regard, behavioral standardized tests are still appearing to support them [25, 26, 27]. However, they are mainly based on the final users feedback due to the SSL immaturity [3] and lack of reliable virtual prototyping approaches contrasted by experimental means [20, 21]. Therefore, methodologies based on simulation and experimental techniques are a still clear demand to improve the issues previously identified and establish standardized assessment protocols for their analysis in industrial environments, where the LED junction temperature is one of the main parameters to be monitored [28, 29].

All such protocols become more relevant and necessary

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when facing the thermal design of compact SSL systems, as occurs for instance, in retrofit lamps [19, 30]. Usually, in such systems, all their parts are enclosed in small embodiments, which restrict the optimum thermal exchange with their surroundings. Moreover, the current trends in LED packaging and driver electronics worsen this thermal management scenario, as they address the following targets: cost reduction, compactness, high level integration in the SSL system, and driver complexity increase due to the inclusion of smart and protection new functionalities [5, 31]. Thus, the thermal interaction between LEDs and the rest of the lamp heat sources cannot be easily avoided by keeping them thermally separated from each other. In this respect, LED driving strategies can provide a solution mainly by lowering the heat generation in the driver components and LED devices. As a matter of fact, LEDs can be externally driven with a constant current and low voltage, or with a constant high voltage and low current. High-Voltage (HV) LEDs have a turn-on voltage that is closer to the mains supply than their Low-Voltage (LV) counterparts. This eliminates some driver electronic components, simplifies its design, reduces its cost, and increases its reliability (e.g., electrolytic capacitors suppression). As a main advantage, HV-LEDs have a smaller forward current than the LV ones [11]. This allows a more uniform current distribution within the die, favoring the LED behavior at die level. However, the HV-LEDs efficiency deteriorates [11]. In this framework, the driver topology selection becomes crucial when an efficient low cost converter is required and the power supplied to the LEDs is targeted to be around 10 W. [5] Therefore, simulation and experimental techniques are once more mandatory to carry out such a trade-off analysis, as well as to find out highly efficient and low cost driver topologies showing a stable electrical output independent from their thermal working conditions.

As a response to all such open quests, this work addresses all them along the thermal design and assessment of an A-60 retrofit lamp oriented to provide a high lumen output for a given LED technology (i.e., LV or HV). Namely, the present research deepens into and proposes solutions to the following aspects: heatsink optimization process and experimental thermal assessment at SSL system level with a lower time consumption, higher accuracy, and better thermal design. Concretely, the lamp heat removal strategy is enhanced by the simulation methodology presented in [19], which performs an in-depth thermal characterization of all lamp materials and their boundary conditions. In contrast to [19], the present study optimizes the lamp thermal management strategy and explores the electrothermal suitability of low cost converter topologies for driving LV- and HV-LEDs, inferring some thermal design guidelines for each driver board and their integration within the lamp. This is interesting as a single design approach can be used for both converters, always searching for improving the thermal path from the driver towards the heatsink. Such solutions pass to reduce the thermal resistance towards the heatsink, in contrast to the usual approaches leaving the driver board enclosed within the lamp without further analysis. Moreover, it presents an non-invasive alternative way to extract and correct the LEDs junction temperature by means of a simple model based on the

LED thermal resistance measurement with temperature. This approach contrast to that commonly based on direct monitoring of thermosensitive parameter, as presented in [29], at risk of affecting the SSL system thermal distribution. According to the targeted driver output power ($\sim 10\text{W}$), two topologies are selected and analyzed [5]: Flyback (electrically isolated, LV, with electrolytic capacitors) and buck-boost (non-isolated, HV, without electrolytic capacitors). To check the thermal design of the new lamp, the temperature is measured at specific locations by attaching thermocouples and InfraRed (IR) thermography, providing a solution to such assessment and LED junction temperature measurement needs previously outlined. For their benchmarking, the obtained results are compared to those extracted from a retrofit lamp awarded by the iF china prize in 2010 [32], which has been established since then, as a design reference for A-60 light bulbs. Although other interesting design parameters (e.g., color rendering index or light intensity distribution) have been taken into account and raised with respect to the reference lamp, this work is focused only on the thermal design. In addition, a new approach to evaluate the LEDs junction temperature by thermally monitoring the LED board backside is presented and used for the lamp thermal assessment. To show all this, the paper has been organized as follows. Section II describes the new lamp, its optimization approach, and its thermal evaluation by using a single LED board driven at different forward current ratings. Besides, an analytic thermal model capable to calculate the LED junction temperature, considering the thermal resistance dependence on the LED board backside temperature, is also pointed out. Section III presents the thermal guidelines followed for the design of the LV and HV drivers, as well as their electrical and thermal characterization at several external temperatures to inspect the drivers suitability for the proposed application. Such thermal guidelines have been derived from the simulation results of the model developed in Section II. Section IV reports the thermal assessment of the drivers placed within the heatsink by following several thermal management solutions at an external temperature of 90°C representative of their worse working conditions within a luminaire. Finally, Section V draws the main conclusions of the work.

II. LAMP THERMAL MANAGEMENT IMPROVEMENT

A. Lamp parts and heat removal optimization procedure

Fig. 1 shows the parts of the LED lamp used as a design reference. It corresponds to a MasterLED Glow lamp [32], which features a power consumption of 6.3 W and a light output of 470 lm. According to Fig. 1, this lamp includes six LV-LEDs serially connected on a Printed Circuit Board (PCB) or LED board, a light dispersion-conversion system made of polycarbonate filled with phosphor (referred to as dome in Fig. 1), and a driver board with the IC device (or IC driver) and other electronic components onto a PCB substrate. As for its thermal extraction system, a thin hollow cone (heatsink thermal cone) acts as a heat spreader and presents axial fins (heatsink fins) at the driver placement location (driver housing). On top, the heatsink thermal cone is covered with a reflective material to improve the lamp light efficiency. Fig. 1

Fig. 1. Reference lamp parts breakdown.

also depicts a Thermal Interface Material (TIM) between the LED board and heatsink, a driver support/shell, and an E27 cap. All such items play a role in the heat removal from the LEDs, dome, and driver to ambient as deeply discussed in [19] and should be taken into account in the lamp thermal design.

From this initial structure, several efforts have been addressed to improve the light output performance, while reducing the lamp manufacturing cost and respecting the reliability standards. To reach higher light output levels without improving the LED efficacy or increasing the LEDs number in an LED board, the electrical power supplied with the driver to the LEDs can be increased. To meet such a requirement, the lamp thermal management strategy has been revisited and redesigned. Among all heat removal techniques, natural-convection heatsinks are still the mainstream approach and the best suited solution to face thermal management problems in industrial products due to its higher reliability and lower cost [33]. Concretely, current trends for low power consumption lamps ($< 10\text{ W}$) define optimized channels within a transparent heatsink (finless design), but this is not possible for final applications requiring higher dissipation at low manufacturing costs, as requested in the present case. For all such reasons, the new heatsink has been conceived as a non-transparent hollow thick cylinder presenting external axial fins and a circular horizontal base on top. With this geometry, the driver board can be easily embedded within and the LED board mounted on top of the circular horizontal base. Thereby, both the LED and driver boards are more efficiently cooled down in comparison to the thermal management strategy proposed in the reference lamp, as the thermal resistance and interfaces are extremely reduced (see Fig. 1). Taking all this into account, the heatsink shape has been thermally optimized by finite volume simulations using ANSYS software. In the heatsink itself, the Fourier's heat conduction and radiative heat transfer are taken into account, treating the heatsink surface as diffuse and grey. As for natural convection, the air is assumed to be an ideal gas, whose density follows the Boussinesq model, and is contained in a cylinder-like volume larger enough to impose as infinite boundary conditions at its edges a fixed ambient temperature T_{amb} without air movement. Its flow is described by the conservation of mass, momentum (i.e.,

Navier-Stokes equation under gravitational force), and energy differential equations, prescribing the same boundary conditions in the heatsink surface as those defined in [13, 14, 15]. All such matters regarding to fluid dynamics have been computed with ANSYS fluent software using the so-called algorithm SIMPLE (Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations), [13, 16] which couples the air velocity and pressure. This heat exchange mechanism has been optimized to minimize the maximum temperature at a given location \vec{r}_{hs} on the heatsink surface fins ($T_{hs,max}(\vec{r}_{hs})$), while n heat sources are dissipating electrical power into heat ($P_{losses,i}$), in such a way that the i -th heat source produce an amount of $P_{losses,i}$ in average ($\langle P_{losses,i} \rangle$), i.e.:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n dM_i(\vec{r}_{hs}) \langle P_{losses,i} \rangle / A_{HS,i} = h_{conv}(\vec{r}_{hs}) (T_{hs,max}(\vec{r}_{hs}) - T_{amb}) dA + \varepsilon(\vec{r}_{hs}) F (T_{hs,max}^4(\vec{r}_{hs}) - T_{amb}^4) dA, \quad (1)$$

where dM_i is a differential of the fraction of $P_{losses,i}$ coming from an i -th heat source exchanged in a differential of surface dA on top of the heatsink. On the other hand, $A_{HS,i}$, $h_{conv}(\vec{r}_{hs})$, dA , F , and $\varepsilon(\vec{r}_{hs})$ correspond to the area of the i -th heat source traversed by $P_{losses,i}$, the convection exchange coefficient at the heatsink location \vec{r}_{hs} , the heatsink total area in contact with air, the radiation view factor, and the heatsink surface emissivity, respectively. In turn, $h_{conv}(\vec{r}_{hs})$ depends among other variables, on the spacing between the heatsink fins s , which can be maximized under natural convection conditions with the heatsink geometry design. To better link the geometrical parameters to the heat exchange, the following equation is inferred from (1) in terms of average values expressed in brackets:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n M_i \langle q_{HS,i} \rangle = \langle h_{conv} \rangle (\langle T_{hs} \rangle - T_{amb}) A + \langle \varepsilon F \rangle (\langle T_{hs}^4 \rangle - T_{amb}^4) A, \quad (2)$$

where A is the heatsink area in contact to the air. $\langle q_{HS,i} \rangle$ corresponds to the average heat flux exchanged in the heatsink due to the i -th heat source. From (1) and (2), A and s are identified as the optimization parameters to reduce both $T_{hs,max}(\vec{r}_{hs})$ and $\langle T_{hs} \rangle$.

To minimize $T_{hs,max}(\vec{r}_{hs})$ with ANSYS, such an optimization process has been performed in two steps by using a Design of Experiments (DOE) scheme. Firstly, the heatsink thermal behavior is simulated in a simplified way to reduce its computation time. With this aim, the heatsink has been simulated as a solid cylinder (heatsink core) with axial rectangular fins presenting an horizontal circular base on top, as Figs 2a and 2b indicate. To emulate both the LED board and driver power dissipation ($P_{losses,LEDs}$ and $P_{losses,driver}$, respectively), an equivalent heat source of 10 W is located at the heatsink core center. This approximation is not critical, as the thickness and number of fins only depend on the sum of $P_{losses,LEDs}$ and $P_{losses,driver}$, which allows for a comparative study among several driver board dimensions according to their cost and compactness. Concerning the material thermal properties, the heatsink core is modeled as a metal (i.e., Aluminum), while the axial rectangular fins are considered as a high thermal conductive polymer. With this structure, the s parameter is maximized by setting the appropriate value for

the fin parameters, i.e., fin number (F), length (L), and thickness (W), accounting for several heatsink inner diameters (d), as shown in Fig. 2b. In fact, d provides a representative value of the driver housing diameter, while D corresponds to the total diameter of the heatsink and the lamp (see Fig 2b). Thus, the air volume corresponding to s relates to W, F, L, d, and H, as $s \approx [(2\pi/F)(L + d) - W] LH$, while $A \approx \pi(d^2/4 + (d/2 + L)^2) + H(\pi d - FW) + F(3WH + 2LH)$. In this DOE process, D and H have been respectively set for 60 and 50 mm, as they are the maximum allowable sizes so as to achieve the specified light intensity distribution and be compatible with the final lamp maximum dimensions based on the A-60 standard [34]. Moreover, H also fixes the maximum length of the driver board. As for L and d, two values have been considered according to two possible driver board sizes: a small driver board with expensive components (d=33 mm and L=17 mm), or a cheaper option with bigger components (d=40 mm and L=10 mm). In that range, it is not plausible that a value for L between 10 mm and 17 mm will give a much higher temperature difference, also leading to a comparative study between both boards. The rest of fin parameters (F and W) have been varied within a certain range to make the fin manufacturable. As a summary, Fig. 2c depicts the simulation results for the above described parameters. In the most expensive and compact driver board case (L=17 mm), the lowest temperature (73.6°C) for this structure is gained for F=24 fins and W=2 mm. Conversely, for the low cost driver board (L=10 mm), the lowest temperature (77°C) is ensured for F=16 and W=4 mm. The low cost driver scenario offers a slightly higher operating temperatures (around 4°C), making it suitable for the case studied in this work. Thus, L=10mm, D=60 mm, H=50 mm, F=16 fins and W=4 mm are selected as heatsink design parameters for the lamp.

Secondly, a more detailed lamp simulation based on the approach presented in [19] has been performed considering other constraints (e.g., illumination angle or light intensity distribution), the previous fin optimization results (i.e., L=10mm, D=60 mm, H=50 mm, F=16 fins and W=4 mm), the fins shape and an air cavity within the hollow cylinder for the driver placement (i.e., driver housing). In such a model, further heat sources have been considered: the driver board with all its elements, the LEDs, bulb, and dome. Moreover, all thermal properties (thermal conductivity and emissivity) concerning all involved materials have been previously measured and included in the model. [19] This has led to the heatsink and lamp final design depicted in Fig. 3. This figure shows the thermally optimized new lamp, in which its color rendering index, light intensity distribution have also been enhanced by an adequate geometric design of the bulb and heatsink, especially in the axial fins shape. From a thermal point of view, the main modifications performed in comparison to the reference lamp design are: the heatsink thermal cone with axial trapezoidal fins has been replaced with a thicker Aluminum hollow cylinder (referred to as Al lining) with highly thermal conductivity polymer fins. To reduce its manufacturing cost, it has been made as a single part by means of an injection molding approach, without any additional assembly process. Such a model, jointly with that of the reference lamp derived in [19], is used to propose a

Fig. 2 (a) Simulated structure, (b) parameters definition in the structure, (c) optimized parameter results for: L=17 mm and L=10mm.

Fig. 3. New lamp parts breakdown.

thermal aware design of the driver boards in III.

B. Heatsink experimental evaluation using LED boards

To demonstrate the improvement gained in II.A, the steady state thermal distribution has been measured in the new and reference lamps using as a heat source an LED board driven at different forward current levels (I_F). Thereby, orientative I_F values for safely driving an LED board and reaching the required light output levels are also explored for the LV-driver scenario presented in III. In this evaluation, the driver board has not been considered, as the driver housing is different in

Fig. 4. Total radiant flux for a single Lumiled Rebel LXML-PR01-0500 as a function of: a) I_F at 25°C and b) thermal pad temperature [35]. Locations thermally monitored with thermocouples in the reference (c) and new (d) lamp designs, also indicating the color and symbol codes used in Fig. 5.

each lamp and thermal management strategies for the new driver boards will be inferred from such results. For such reasons, the driver thermal effects are analyzed in IV. In such heatsink preliminary tests, an LED board composed by 6 Lumiled Rebel LEDs (LXML-PR01-0500, low voltage LEDs) has been mounted within each lamp to make the results comparable. As a matter of fact, this LED model has been selected as it has been employed in the reference lamp. In these thermal measurements, the LED junction temperature ($T_{J,LED}$) is aside from other locations in the lamp, one of the most important parameters to assess the LEDs proper operation at several I_F . Unfortunately, $T_{J,LED}$ cannot be directly measured as no direct access to the LEDs is possible when the lamp is mounted. Thus, $T_{J,LED}$ is derived by using the bottom board temperature below one LED (T_{BotBRD}), $P_{losses,LEDs}$ that depends on T_{BotBRD} and I_F (i.e., $P_{losses,LEDs}(T_{BotBRD}, I_F)$), and the board junction-to-case thermal resistance as a function of T_{BotBRD} ($R_{th,j-c}(T_{BotBRD})$), as this relationship states [19]:

$$T_{J,LED} = \frac{1}{6} P_{losses,LEDs}(T_{BotBRD}, I_F) R_{th,j-c}(T_{BotBRD}) + T_{BotBRD}, \quad (3)$$

where T_{BotBRD} is considered as the reference temperature. With regards to $P_{losses,LEDs}$ calculation, the power transformed into light or radiant flux (P_{opt}) is required, apart from the

power supplied to the LED board (P_{IN}). P_{opt} is determined taking into account its dependence on I_F and the thermal pad temperature from the LEDs datasheet [35], as presented in Fig. 4. The normalized total radiant flux (P_{opt}/P_0) versus I_F at 25°C for a single Lumiled Rebel LXML-PR01-0500 is extracted from [35] (white square data points in Fig. 4a) and the following expression is determined by performing a polynomial fitting to this data (black solid line in Fig. 4a), as Fig. 4a shows:

$$\frac{P_{opt}}{P_0}(I_F) = 2.34 \times 10^{-3} + 3.75 \times 10^{-3} I_F - 3.43 \times 10^{-6} I_F^2 + 3.40 \times 10^{-9} I_F^3 - 1.37 \times 10^{-12} I_F^4. \quad (4)$$

On the other hand, the LED thermal effects can be compensated assuming that T_{BotBRD} is almost the same than the thermal pad temperature. According to this, the temperature correction (Γ) reported in [35] (red circled data points, see Fig. 4b) is represented versus T_{BotBRD} and a polynomial fitting is carried out (red solid line, see Fig. 4b) to derive the following relationship:

$$\Gamma(T_{BotBRD}) = 1.00342 - 3.37 \times 10^{-4} T_{BotBRD} + 1.20 \times 10^{-5} T_{BotBRD}^2 - 1.62 \times 10^{-7} T_{BotBRD}^3 + 4.04 \times 10^{-10} T_{BotBRD}^4. \quad (5)$$

Thus, $P_{losses,LEDs}$ (i.e., $P_{IN} - P_{opt}$) can be written as function of T_{BotBRD} and I_F as follows:

$$P_{losses,LEDs}(T_{BotBRD}, I_F) = V_F I_F - 6 P_0 \Gamma(T_{BotBRD}) \frac{P_{opt}}{P_0}(I_F), \quad (6)$$

where V_F is the LED forward voltage drop. Finally, $R_{th,j-c}(T_{BotBRD})$ has been measured with a system presented in [19], where T_{BotBRD} is uniformly imposed with a hot plate and measured with a thermocouple. From such measurements, the next expression for $R_{th,j-c}(T_{BotBRD})$ is derived:

$$R_{th,j-c}(T_{BotBRD}) = 11.16 - 3.22 \times 10^{-2} T_{BotBRD} + 8.84 \times 10^{-4} T_{BotBRD}^2. \quad (7)$$

Regarding to the experimental details for the tests, the LED board driving has been performed with an SMU Keithley 2410, ranging I_F from 100 to 700 mA (typical values for LV-LEDs). As for their thermal experimental boundary conditions, the lamp orientation has been kept upwards, reproducing the air steady state convection of the simulations. To monitor the temperature at specific locations in the reference and new lamps, as respectively depicted in Figs. 4c and 4d, the beads of several K-type thermocouples have been glued in that measurement points with thermal conductive epoxy after performing small drills. Their temperature acquisition has been performed using a Keithley 3706 system (switch multimeter) with a plug-in card (model 3721), which ensures an accuracy in temperature readings of 1°C in the measuring interval from -150 to 1372°C [36]. To explore a wider area on the bulb, a set of spots on its surface at different heights have been monitored in both lamps with an IR camera (SC5500 Flir camera), as shown in Fig. 4d. They have been

Fig. 5. Dependence of the temperature in several lamp parts on I_F for the reference (a) and new (b) designs.

located on top (IR-top), lateral side (IR-side) and bottom (IR-bot) of the bulb surface. All acquisitions have been performed after waiting for 2000 s to ensure the steady state regime. As a summary, Fig. 5 presents all thermocouple measurements and the extracted $T_{J,LED}$ for both lamps, i.e., the reference (Fig. 5a) and new (Fig. 5b) designs, depending on I_F . This figure demonstrates that the top dome temperature is similar in both lamps (around 130°C). By contrast, in the rest of monitored locations, the temperature lessens in the new design, $T_{J,LED}$ also being reduced a 17.8% (significant improvement). To analyze the influence of the new heatsink on the bulb temperature at the highest I_F value (i.e., 700 mA), the IR camera has been used. Under such driving condition, such results have been compared to those measured in the reference lamp (see Fig. 4c). It has been observed that the temperatures in the new lamp have lowered at the IR-top and IR-bot spots (temperature decreases 13.12°C and 7.38°C, respectively), while are almost equal at the IR-side spot in both lamps (difference lower than 1°C). Therefore, the new design really outperform the reference lamp thermal behavior.

III. DRIVERS DESCRIPTION, THERMAL DESIGN AND ELECTRO-THERMAL CHARACTERIZATION

Prior to address the driver board thermal design, its output electrical characteristics and the converter topologies studied should be defined. The driver output electrical characteristics have been fixed according to the LED boards used for their thermal evaluation. To be compatible with the thermal lamp design detailed in II.A, two low cost LED boards have been implemented with six LV and HV Rebel Lumiled LEDs (i.e., LXML-PR02-1100 and LXAC-PW27, respectively) using a PCB as a substrate. For such loads, the LV and HV LED boards require to be driven at least, at ratings of 18V / 620mA and 110V / 80mA, respectively, to reach the lumen output targeted in each case (799 and 460 Lm, respectively). For such electrical ratings, to $P_{losses,LEDs}$ values of 6.36 W and 8.11 W have been achieved for LV and HV scenarios, respectively. As another design requirement, the LED driving must be kept stable and independent from T_{amb} . To this end, the following LV and HV driver technologies have been proposed with an accurate selection of their components. The LV-driver is based on a flyback converter (isolated solution) with a primary sensing regulation and quasi-resonant zero voltage switching to increase its efficiency [37]. It almost supports all available TRIAC/MOSFET dimmers and integrates an active bleeder control to optimize its performance and size. On the other hand, the HV-driver is based on a buck-boost converter [38] with the following benefits: non-isolated, snubber-less, and low cost. Nevertheless, other aspects make them less attractive than the LV solution. In terms of reliability, the HV-driver presents a high stress on the output diode, whereas with regards to light efficiency, the HV-LEDs show a lower yield in contrast to its low voltage counterparts. Thus, such differences between HV and LV drivers make interesting their comparative study to determine which technology much better fits in the proposed design. Notice that both drivers present a certain ripple at their output current and voltage, and for this reason, the ratings for LED board driving will be ensured and given in RMS (Root Mean Square) values. As for the thermal design, several thermal vias and lateral metal tracks have been conceived in both boards to enhance the heat removal towards the heatsink Al lining (as proposed in II.A). Moreover, both driver boards have been devised with a trapezoidal shape to better fit and thermally contact in its housing thanks to the indentations performed within the heatsink Al lining internal lateral sides. This thermal contact is also favored by the lateral metal tracks of the driver board. Therefore, the components dissipating the most have been located close to such metal tracks, when possible, or their heat removal has been assisted incorporating thermal vias close to them. To enhance their cooling down through the lateral metal tracks, a PCB with an anisotropic thermal conductivity has been used to foster the in-plane heat conduction towards the heatsink Al lining. All such strategies have been verified with the simulation model demonstrated in II.A for the whole lamp. The heat dissipation values for all components of each driver board have been retrieved from their datasheets and included in the simulation model. As a result, a temperature reduction on the LEDs and driver board of 6% and 15% is respectively obtained when

TABLE I
MAIN ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS MEASURED ON LV- AND HV-DRIVERS

Parameters	LV-Driver	HV-Driver
$V_{IN\ RMS}$ (V)	221	219
$I_{IN\ RMS}$ (mA)	64	54
$P_{IN\ MEAN}$ (W)	14.2	11
PF ()	0.99	0.93
η ()	0.794	0.825
$V_{OUT\ RMS}$ (V)	18.36	110.20
$I_{OUT\ RMS}$ (mA)	700	82
$P_{OUT\ MEAN}$ (W)	11.5	9.04
$P_{losses,driver}$ (W)	2.70	1.96

Fig. 6. Top view of the LV-driver faces showing the locations monitored by IR thermography.

comparing simulation results of the new design to those of the reference lamp.

To experimentally assess the results achieved with the outlined thermal strategies, both drivers have been electro-thermally evaluated considering T_{amb} values in the range of 30°C-100°C. As discussed in [19], a controlled ambient temperature enclosure (300×400×180 mm³) with an IR window and an IR-camera (SC5500 Flir camera) has been used to this end. Depending on the driver, the previously mentioned Rebel Lumiled LEDs (i.e., LXML-PR02-1100 for LV-driver and LXAC-PW27 for HV-driver) have been employed as LED loads, keeping them outside the enclosure to only evaluate the driver thermal performance. With this set-up, the driver board electro-thermal characteristics have been firstly analyzed at $T_{amb}=30^\circ\text{C}$, and such results have been taken as a reference to analyze the T_{amb} effects on the driver performance. Table I reports in RMS units, the main electrical characteristics achieved for each driver board at $T_{amb}=30^\circ\text{C}$: input voltage and current ($V_{IN\ RMS}$ and $I_{IN\ RMS}$), output voltage and current ($V_{OUT\ RMS}$ and $I_{OUT\ RMS}$). This table also presents the mean input and output real powers of the driver ($P_{IN\ MEAN}$ and $P_{OUT\ MEAN}$, respectively), jointly with the power factor (PF), the efficiency (η), and $P_{losses,driver}$. This table also confirms that the minimum RMS output ratings required for driving the aforementioned LEDs are achieved. In addition, comparable values are obtained when the $P_{losses,LEDs}$ and $P_{losses,driver}$ are summed: for the LV and HV cases present 9.6 W and 10.07 W, respectively, validating the values used in II.A for the heatsink design. In comparison to the LV case, the HV-driver has a lower PF and a higher η due to the different

Fig. 7. Time evolution of LV driver components and steady state thermal images (inset) for faces A (a) and B (b) at $I_f=700\text{mA}$ and $T_{amb}=30^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 8. Analyzed dimmable HV-driver, top (Face A) and bottom (Face B) views and the locations monitored by IR thermography.

energy conversion approaches followed in each situation. As for the LV driver thermal behavior at $T_{amb}=30^\circ\text{C}$, Fig. 6 indicates the electronic component locations thermally monitored for each driver face. The time evolution of such a thermal information is presented in Fig. 7, together with the driver thermal map in steady state (insets). Looking at the thermal images of Fig. 7, the hottest components are both the snubber and damper resistors (i.e., LT5A and LT2A,

Fig. 9 Time evolution of HV-driver components and steady state thermal images (inset) for faces A (a) and B (b) at $I_f=700\text{mA}$ and $T_{\text{amb}}=30^\circ\text{C}$.

respectively) on Face A (Fig. 7a); and the output diode (i.e., LT4B) on Face B (Fig. 7b). With regards to HV driver thermal results at $T_{\text{amb}} = 30^\circ\text{C}$, Fig. 8 points out for each driver face, the locations thermally monitored for each electronic component. Fig. 9 depicts their time evolution, as well as a thermal map (inset) of the driver under working conditions at $T_{\text{amb}} = 30^\circ\text{C}$. In this figure, the temperature distribution over the electrical components is shown for each face, depicting the hot spots. In this case, the observed hot spots correspond to the input resistors (HT6A and HT7A, Face A) and their terminals (HT4B and HT5B, Face B), reaching temperature values of 78°C and 73°C , respectively.

When T_{amb} is increased within the considered thermal range, the drivers electrical and thermal characteristics evolve as follows. In the LV scenario, the main electrical parameters detailed in Table I are kept almost constant, except for η . η slightly decreases with T_{amb} due to the components thermal dependence: $\eta = 0.774$ is achieved at $T_{\text{amb}}=100^\circ\text{C}$, whereas at $T_{\text{amb}}=30^\circ\text{C}$, $\eta = 0.795$. When T_{amb} increases from 30°C to 100°C , the temperature deviation on the driver Face A remains constant. However, in Face B, the hottest spot is changed at 100°C : the IC driver or device (LT3B, 144°C) becomes hotter than the output diode (LT4B, 137°C). In the HV-driver, η slightly increases with T_{amb} . Besides, the heat dissipation of

the driver board depends on T_{amb} : at $T_{\text{amb}}=100^\circ\text{C}$, $I_{\text{OUT RMS}}$ lowers a 10% from its reference value at $T_{\text{amb}}=30^\circ\text{C}$. In all considered scenarios, the driver hot spots remain at the same areas, and the temperature deviation over the driver surface is almost constant (only 5°C variations). From such results, a good thermal design has been obtained for both drivers, also identifying the thermal monitoring points for being considered in the following section.

IV. DRIVER THERMAL EVALUATION WITH THE DESIGNED HEAT REMOVAL APPROACH

So as to integrate the driver board into the lamp, several solutions have been evaluated to minimize the contact thermal resistance between the heatsink and the driver, as well as to improve the heat removal in the driver housing. With this aim, the driver configurations depicted in Fig. 10 have been studied as thermal management strategies. Namely, the driver is unclamped to the heatsink (see Fig. 10a, Test 1), clamped to the heatsink without and with a TIM on the metal tracks (see Figs. 10b and 10c and referred to as Tests 2 and 3, respectively), and also surrounded (see Fig. 10d, Test 4) by a high thermally conductive potting material (i.e., dry silica sand). In all them, the lamp is considered without the dome, bulb and LED board (i.e., without parts 1, 2, and 3 shown in Fig. 3), being referred to as DLamp (i.e., Driver Lamp) from now on. The set-up used to carry out such an analysis is presented in Fig. 11. As stated in III.A, the ensemble DLamp-driver board is introduced within the controlled ambient temperature enclosure, whereas the LED loads are placed outside onto a heatsink. As for the measurements thermal boundary conditions, the ensemble DLamp-driver is downwards oriented under free-convection. To reproduce the thermal working conditions, T_{amb} is fixed at 90°C within the controlled ambient temperature enclosure, as this is a typical value reached in closed luminaires. Additionally, this temperature allows evaluating whether the electrolytic capacitors used in the LV-driver can be working under such thermal conditions. Throughout the thermal measurements, both drivers have been switched on at a full load and the thermocouple readings have been carried in steady state, after a stabilization time of 7200 s.

As carried out in II.B, K Type thermocouples have been attached with conductive epoxy at specific locations in the DLamp and driver board, and acquired with the switch multimeter Keithley 3706 using a plug-in card (model 3721). Such locations correspond in the case of the DLamp, to those already used in II.B (see Fig. 4d), whereas in the LV and HV-driver boards, they refer to those identified in III as the highest temperature positions within the hot spots. Namely, in the LV-driver case, the following components/locations are monitored (see Fig. 6): damper resistor (LT2A), Snubber resistor (LT5A), the hottest active bleeder resistor (LT1B), IC driver or device (LT3B), and output diode (LT4B). Whereas in the HV-driver, the following electronic components are locally measured (see Fig. 8): RIN1 (HT6A), RIN2 (HT7A), output resistor (HT1B), diode bridge (HT3B), IC driver or device (HT7B), and bipolar transistor (BJT) (HT8B).

To better compare them, Tables II and III summarize the results obtained for LV and HV scenarios, respectively. In

Fig. 10 Driver board placing configurations: a) free or unclamped, b) clamped to the heatsink and without TIM at the board metal tracks, c) clamped and with TIM and, d) clamped, with TIM, and the housing filled with a potting material (dry silica sand, in this case).

Fig. 11. Set-up used to analyze the different driver board placing configurations.

general, the LV-driver reaches higher temperatures than the HV one, pointing out in the driver housing, a temperature difference between each case of almost 10°C. As for the DLamp parts, similar values are obtained in all tests, varying within a 5°C interval. For the LV scenario (see Table II), it has been observed that when the driver is clamped to the heatsink and without TIM in the metal tracks (i.e., Test 2) instead of leaving it unclamped (i.e., Test 1), the driver components show a noticeable temperature decrease, reaching in the IC device a reduction of 19°C. Conversely, the temperature in the monitored parts of the DLamp remains practically unchanged, depicting variations of 2-3°C. Similar trends are measured when clamping the LV-driver, using a TIM in the metal tracks (Test 3), and when considering dry silica sand as a potting material (i.e., Test 4). In comparison to Test 1 results, the temperature in the main lamp parts is slightly lowered within a range of 5°C, but in some of the driver components, it falls down up to around 25°C or more (see LT3B: IC device and LT5B: Snubber resistor). Concerning the HV scenario (Table III), similar trends to those described in the LV case are obtained. However, the thermal improvement resulting from using the board clamped and with TIM in the metal tracks (Test 2) is not important in this case. Furthermore, when using dry silica sand as a potting material (Test 4), the temperature decreases in comparison to Test 1 results, up to around 10°C or slightly more in all driver components. To extend the analysis performed in the HV driver, another potting material has been considered: Magnesium Oxide

TABLE II
THERMAL RESULTS FOR THE DIFFERENT PLACEMENT CONFIGURATIONS OF THE LV-DRIVER BOARD INSIDE THE LAMP (IN °C)

THERMO-COUPLE NAME, ACCORDING TO FIGS. 3, 4d AND 6	TEST 1: FREE	TEST 2: CLAMP	TEST 3: CLAMP TIM	TEST 4: CLAMP TIM POTTING
SPREADER (5): Heat spreader	102.68	101.24	101.41	103.90
AL LINING (6): Al lining	104.34	102.65	100.86	103.36
HS1 (7): Heatsink	104.55	102.85	101.02	103.53
HS2 (8): Al lining	104.46	100.62	99.22	101.32
SHELL (9): Shell	104.08	101.72	99.15	102.60
HOUSING (10): Driver housing	111.11	108.57	101.74	103.98
AMBIENT (11): Ambient	90	90	90	90
LT3B: IC driver or device	145.32	125.83	121.63	118.89
LT1B: Act. bleeder resistor	135.71	121.31	117.49	117.93
LT4B: Output diode	135.66	130.73	127.77	123.77
LT2A: Damper resistor	142.38	133.83	130.03	133.16
LT5A: Snubber resistor	145.06	132.96	128.74	120.26

TABLE III
THERMAL RESULTS FOR THE DIFFERENT PLACEMENT CONFIGURATIONS OF THE HV-DRIVER BOARD INSIDE THE LAMP (IN °C)

THERMO-COUPLE NAME, ACCORDING TO FIGS. 3, 4d AND 8	TEST 1: FREE	TEST 2: CLAMP	TEST 3: CLAMP TIM	TEST 4: CLAMP TIM POTTING 1 (Dry Silica)	TEST 5: CLAMP TIM POTTING 2 (MgO)
SPREADER (5): Heat spreader	96.57	96.44	95.99	94.22	97.34
AL LINING (6): Al lining	96.48	96.68	95.89	94.12	96.98
HS1 (7): Heatsink	96.55	96.42	95.97	94.22	97.34
HS2 (8): Lining	96.54	93.69	95.96	94.18	96.59
SHELL (9): Shell	97.51	96.02	96.39	95.05	98.44
HOUSING (10): Driver housing	99.40	98.26	97.28	95.85	98.80
AMBIENT (11): Ambient	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00
HT6A: RIN 1	142.77	142.73	138.22	132.19	137.65
HT7A: RIN2	141.70	141.84	134.06	124.91	126.46
HT3B: Diode bridge	126.63	125.30	124.32	118.31	123.32
HT8B: Bipolar transistor (BJT)	110.65	108.83	106.51	100.33	103.42
HT7B: IC driver or device	109.13	108.18	105.48	99.67	102.50
HT1B: Output resistor	108.56	108.14	107.04	101.25	103.41

(MgO) powder (Test 5). This material presents a lower thermal conductivity and cost than dry silica sand, and could be used as a potting material in the HV case, since this driver reach lower temperature values under operation than the LV one. The Test 5 results reproduce the behaviors previously outlined in the driver and DLamp temperatures, which reaches in general, higher temperatures in contrast to Test 4 within a range of 3-5°C.

As a summary, the heat extraction is improved when clamping the drivers to the heatsink, using a TIM in the board

lateral metal tracks, and considering a potting material in the housing. As a result, the temperature in the driver board components reduces between 20°C in the LV case and around 10°C in the HV scenario. By contrast, the temperature in the DLamp monitored locations only diminishes at most, 5°C. Comparing the driver behavior for this thermal configuration, the maximum peak temperature is similar in both drivers (133.16°C for LT2A: Damper Resistor and 132.19°C for HT6A:RIN1). However, the temperature in the other electronic components extremely lowers for HV-driver (up to almost 20°C in the IC-device). Therefore, it is expected that the HV-driver would provide a better reliability level and lifetime expectancy than the LV one. Unfortunately, HV-LEDs cannot provide a high output lumen as their LV counterparts, restricting the HV approach as a promising solution for retrofit lamps in view of the HV LED efficacy improvement in the next years.

V. CONCLUSION

This work reports on the thermal design and experimental assessment of a low cost retrofit LED lamp for high lumen output using LV and HV LED boards. For this study, a flyback converter has been identified suitable for LV driving, while the back-boost one has been pointed out as the best choice for the HV case. To meet the requirement of high lumen output, the power supplied with the driver to the LEDs has been increased to keep the lamp operative within a certain safety margin. This target has implied to carry out a thermal design of the whole LED lamp and the driver boards, making special focus on the driver integration in the lighting system. With this purpose, the thermal management of the complete lamp has been optimized by a multiscale simulation approach. As a result, a free-convection heatsink has been determined as the lowest cost and most reliable solution. Such a heatsink consists in an Aluminum hollow cylinder with high conductive polymer axial fins, allowing the driver placement within, and presents on top a circular base for mounting the LED board. Furthermore, the driver boards have been also optimized for enhancing the heat removal with thermal vias, lateral thermal metal tracks in contact with heatsink, and using PCB's with in-plane enhanced thermal conductivity.

According to the guidelines derived from simulation results, the heatsink and both driver boards have been implemented and experimentally assessed. The temperature distribution in the new designed LED lamp, heatsink and driver boards has been measured with thermocouples and an IR camera. This has been performed throughout several comparative analyses in different tests. Firstly, the heat removal efficiency and the thermal behavior of the new lamp has been compared to that of an LED lamp used as a design reference. In this test, a LV LED board has been used as a heat source for the thermal evaluation of both lamps, without considering the drivers. Aside from other monitoring locations, the LEDs junction temperature has been determined with a thermal model developed in this work to study the impact of each design on this parameter. Secondly, the new drivers have also been fully characterized by IR thermography to ensure an electrical behavior independent from their ambient working temperature. Thirdly, several thermal management solutions

have been evaluated to improve the contact thermal resistance and heat exchange between the driver board and the heatsink. They have consisted in several configurations for the driver placement within the lamp. The best strategy has been clamping the board to the heatsink, using a TIM to improve its contact thermal resistance, and surrounding it with a high conductivity potting material.

From the implementation point of view, the proposed heatsink allows obtaining a reduction of the LED junction temperature of 18% respect to the reference lamp, whereas both drivers present similar maximum temperatures around or below 125°C for a working ambient temperature of 90°C. In comparison to the LV-driver, the temperature reached in other electronic components has lowered for the HV-driver. Thus, the HV-driver is preferred in terms of efficiency, lifetime and reliability, as smaller and non-electrolytic capacitors can be used. However, the HV LED board almost halves the lamp lumen output in comparison to the LV approach, which makes the HV solution for retrofit lamps as a something to be contemplated in the next years when HV LEDs will feature the same efficacy than the LV ones. Furthermore, the presented solution can drive LED boards when higher lumen output in retrofit lamps are required, as considered drivers allow delivering higher electrical power to LEDs.

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